

Influence of Television Advertising in Acquiring Cosmetics with Special Reference to Women Consumers in Puducherry

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ABSTRACT

Television advertising helps individual consumers to evaluate different cosmetic products available in the market and to select the best one which fulfils their expectation. The purpose of this study is to find the extent to which women consumers grab information from television advertising. Women take final decision related to acquiring a product and encourage others to accept the decision in their family. Television advertising is one of the best tools in the hands of the marketer, to make the consumer acquire the product. Even though a lot of money is wasted or invested in a television advertisement it detains and coerces individuals to acquire the product. This study aims to find the influence of television advertising on acquiring. In this study, both primary and secondary data were used and the primary data were collected from 100 women consumers in Puducherry. The collected data were analysed by using SPSS software, by using correlation and chi-square test. This study aims to find the significant relationship between television advertising and cosmetics acquired by women consumer and the attributes liked in cosmetics advertisement on television. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between television advertising and cosmetics acquired by women consumer. By using the chi-square test, it was found that there is a significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and occupation of the respondents. It was also found that there is no significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and age, educational qualification, marital status and type of family.

KEYWORDS: Television advertising, cosmetics, women consumers and acquire

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Sriranga (2003) advertisement is the engine of modern economics and is one of the crucial factors influencing the behaviour and life style of modern society. Advertisements portray men, women and children irrespective of the product advertised. Since the Indian women play a dominant role in the purchase of products, many marketers are targeting women and are increasingly portraying them in advertisements. The researchers Ramaswami and Namakumari (2004) in their study observed that advertisers are trying to spread maximum information about products in target market. Therefore, popularity is the aim of advertising. Romaniuk and Sharp (2004) insists that the most used promotional tool in marketing today is advertising. Dhanabhakya and Geetha (2006) explained that advertising stimulates increase in production, wider distribution, and greater availability of goods and services and consequently generates more employment.

Mrudhula (2011) has expressed that advertisements bridge the gap between the companies' products and consumer's thinking. Creative and persuasive advertisements fill the minds of customers with latent information, visa-visa the advertisements that create a negative impact. Creating

advertisements is a herculean task and the process involves great efforts.

Advertising Definition

According to Belch (2004), the word advertising originated from a Latin word 'advertise', which means to turn to. The dictionary meaning of the term is "to give public notice or to announce publicly". Terence (2007) defined advertising as a paid mediated form of communication from an identifiable source, designed to persuade the receiver to take some action, now or in the future.

Television Advertising

Ciochetto (2004) in his study the advertisers find it more effective to use television rather than print media to reach consumers, partly due to low literacy rate. Reactions to TV advertisements seem to be stronger than the reaction to print advertisements. The advertisers find it more effective to use television rather than print media to reach consumers, partly due to low literacy rate. Fam and Waller (2008) have studied about the desired and undesired television commercials in India. They have concluded in their study that the liking and disliking of television commercials are attributed to general Indian values, family values and

religious adherence. Culture plays an important role in monitoring consumer perspectives and attributes. So the marketers must consider the local sensitivities while preparing their advertisement campaign.

According to Latif and Abideen (2011) Advertising through all mediums influence audiences, but television is one of the strongest medium of advertising and due to its mass reach; it can influence not only the individual's attitude, behavior, life style, exposure and in the long run, even the culture of the country. Sathyapriya and Saiganesh (2012) attempted to find out whether television advertisements play a major role in bridging the communication gap between the manufacturers and the consumers. The aim of the study was to examine the behaviour of audience towards selected television advertisements, with the traits liked and disliked by them. Aided recall with ten television advertisements of regional language was used. The study also explored the behaviour of the audience and their preferences in watching television advertisements. According to Krishnakumar and Radha (2014) Ads not only inform the features and benefits of the products. Image of the products, brand and company is also built with the help of effective marketing messages. TV does it effectively with its audio visual strength for the marketers. Quality of the advertising messages increases the involvement level of the audience. This study results revealed that the relevant information is due to ads effectiveness and consumer expectations fulfil through ads in effective manner leads to purchase decision.

Hassan (2015) insists that rural individuals and females like the TV advertisement more than urban residents and male counterparts. Rural residents jointly make a decision with their family members which product to be purchased and they also expect the same quality of the product that is shown in TV advertisement while it is not so with the urban residents. Both genders and residents sense good when they watch the ad of the particular product that they are by now having. The urban citizens do not purchase the product that they don't need. The study proved that there is a significant variation among the rural and urban residents on the issue that TV advertisement; enhance the engagement process of buying. The buying behaviour of female individuals is more influenced by the television advertisements than their male counterparts.

II. Cosmetics

The researcher Neetu Aneja (2014) found that the maximum consumer recall single of their favorite brand. It seems the most effective media for the face and body creams are Radio & Television, their inference was drawn from the fact that the respondents were asked to recall their favorite advertisements 60% respondents recall the advertisement of different brands which were advertised through these media. Also who made a choice of particular brand after being influenced by advertisement most of them were introduced to their brand through T.V and Radio advertisement. It was depicted that television plays an important role as advertising media for face & body creams. The television was most popular media for hair & body oils.

Fatima and Lodhi (2015) revealed that there are two important variables which can influence the buying behaviors of the people but these two factors are not solely reason to change the behaviors of the consumers rather they can contributing in changing the behaviors of the consumers.. In the end we conclude that cosmetic companies

should use attractive and informative content to create the awareness in the consumers and they should not rely on the advertisement for changing the perceptions of the consumers instead they should use new ways of sales promotion or other medium to change the perceptions of the people. It will be easy for any company in cosmetic industry to change the buying behavior of consumer by creating awareness and building strong perception in the mind of their customers.

According to Fowler et. al. (2015) deception not only undermines the credibility of advertising as a whole by making consumers defensive, but also produces damaging effects for the advertisers who are directly responsible for making the claims. The study makes it clear that marketers have a powerful self-interest in upholding the truth in cosmetics advertising. This article presented the genesis and current status of cosmetics claims and suggested that more regulations need to be developed.

Kumar (2016) concluded that mostly respondents are graduates from the 26-35 years age group and from the urban area. Most of the factors influences the customers purchase decision in which life style and value at the top; followed by quality, personality, culture, reference group, occupation, religion, price, brand name and packaging. It also found that customers' satisfaction of branded shampoo at the top; followed by Face Wash, Cream, Nail Polish, Perfumes, Powder, Lipstick, Kajal, Eye shadow, and Face powder. The study also explains the impact of the brand on the consumer mind which influences the buying behaviour of the customer in the context of cosmetics.

Consumer Buyer Behaviour

Nagaraja (2004) stated that the buying behaviour is very much influenced by experience of their own and of their own family. The involvements of his own family members exert maximum influence on his purchases. Consumers were influenced by touch and feel aspect of any promotional activity. According to Engel et al., (2006) consumer buying behaviour is itself is a complex, dynamic issue which cannot be defined easily and commonly. Therefore, the concept of consumer buying behaviour has been defined in different ways by different researchers.

The researcher Rai (2013) found that advertisement worldwide influence the behaviour and attitude formation of consumers not only in India but also worldwide. The consumers of durables products have their motivational sources which are advertisements and study revealed that advertisement motivates them to materialize the purchase of durables. The consumers are induced significantly by advertisements when the target is on quality and price. Purchase attitude and behavior is influenced by variety of advertisements which cover product evaluation and brand recognition. Saluja (2016) concluded that the purchase intention of consumers is influenced by attitude variables. The consumers enjoy shopping mostly with their friends and family members. They are influenced by their friends, family members, celebrities, magazines etc. Quality, comfort, brand are the main criteria's which effect their buying behavior towards fashion apparels. Even all the demographic factors like gender, age, occupation and monthly income don't have any impact on buying behaviour of consumers towards fashion apparels.

According to Lalitha & Panchanatham (2013) advertisements are able to provide awareness and

knowledge about the products, their influence level on the purchasing behaviour is less only. Most people stick on to the concept of buying the product based on past experience as they are little bit reluctant to try new products. Marketers should understand that rural consumer's value for money and they don't believe in exaggeration and flirt in advertisement. Marketers need to understand that advertisement have been able to change the way how consumers look upon the products and brands thereby building an association which goes to an extent of giving rural consumers an expression of getting identified with the product.

III. Objectives of the study

1. To find the impact of television advertising on cosmetics acquired by women consumers in Puducherry.
2. To find the significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and socioeconomic variables.

IV. Hypotheses of the study

1. H₀: There is no significant relationship between television advertising and the cosmetics acquired by women consumers.
2. H₀: There is no significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and age wise classification of the respondents.

VI. Analysis and Interpretation

The frequency distribution of consumer profile based on the various socio-economic variables of women consumers in Puducherry.

Table 1 shows the frequency distribution of consumer profile

S. No.	Consumer Profile	Frequency	Percentage	
1	Age (in years)	Less than 25	32	32
		25 - 30	16	16
		31 - 40	28	28
		41 - 50	8	8
		51 - 60	12	12
		Total	100	100
2	Educational Qualification	HSC	5	5
		Diploma	5	5
		Under Graduate	47	47
		Post Graduate	43	43
		Total	100	100
3	Occupation	Government	7	7
		Private	64	64
		Business	7	7
		Student	12	12
		Housewife	10	10
		Total	100	100
4	Monthly Income	Less than 20,000	13	13
		20,001 - 30,000	7	7
		30,001 - 40,000	9	9
		40,001 - 50,000	2	2
		50,001 - 60,000	36	36
		More than 60,000	33	33
Total	100	100		
5	Marital Status	Married	80	80
		Unmarried	20	20
		Total	100	100
6	Type of Family	Nuclear	69	69
		Joint	31	31
		Total	100	100

3. H₀: There is no significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and educational qualification of the respondents.
4. H₀: There is no significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and the occupation of the respondents.
5. H₀: There is no significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and marital status of the respondents.
6. H₀: There is no significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and the type of family of the respondents.

V. Research Methodology

A sample design is a definite plan for obtaining a sample from a given population. It refers to the technique or the procedure the researcher would adopt in selecting items for the sample. The sample for the study is 100 women consumers from Puducherry district. The sampling technique followed in the study is convenience Sampling. This study was based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data have been collected from the women consumers in Puducherry by using questionnaire. The statistical tools such as correlation and chi-square test are used for analyzing the influence of television advertising on the cosmetics acquired by women consumers in Puducherry.

7	Number of Family Members	Less than 3	28	28
		3 - 4	52	52
		5 - 6	16	16
		7 - 8	3	3
		More than 8	1	1
		Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 shows 32% of the respondents are less than 25 and most of the respondents are graduates. A majority of 64% of the women consumers are working in private concern. It was observed that 36% of the respondent's monthly income is in between Rs.50,000 to Rs.60,000. Nearly 80% of the respondents are married and 69% of the respondents are in the nuclear family. The number of family members in case of 52% of the respondents is 3 – 4 members.

Table 2 shows the variables influencing the purchase decision of women consumers

The variables influencing Purchase decision		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Television Advertisement	37	37
	Family Members	21	21
	Self	6	6
	Friends	24	24
	Work Place	12	12
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that 37% of the respondents agree that the purchase decision of women consumers is influenced by Television Advertisement. Subsequently, the friend's circle plays a major role in selecting the product. According to Singh (2015) majority of youngsters television was the most influential source of advertisement followed by friends/relatives while newspaper, online media and radio. Television was considered the most effective media of advertisements.

Vani et al., (2011) find out which mode of promotion consumer gets attracted, the data pertaining to this is presented in table 12. An examination of the table reveals that, most of the consumers preferred advertisement, celebrity, banners. Majority of the respondents 45% preferred advertisements, 25% of the respondents preferred celebrity endorsements, 20% preferred banners, and 10% preferred other mode of promotion. Advertisement creates attention and stimulates the consumer to buy a particular brand.

Table 3 shows the attributes like very much in cosmetics advertising

Attributes like very much in cosmetics advertising		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Music	46	46
	Artist	21	21
	Concept & Theme	13	13
	Creativity	11	11
	Information	9	9
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it was inferred that women consumer like very much music in cosmetic advertising and then they give more preference to the artist at the time of watching the advertisement. Almost 45% of women consumers like music very much among the various attributes in television advertising. Singh (2015) has observed that celebrity endorsements were the most important feature of television advertising followed by theme, information content and punch lines. Majority of the youngsters follow the famous celebrities and often purchase those products which are endorsed by them.

Table 4 shows the relationship between television advertising and the cosmetics acquired by women consumers in Puducherry.

Correlations			
		Television Advertising	Cosmetics Acquired
Television Advertising	Pearson Correlation	1	.244*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.014
	N	100	100
Cosmetics Acquired	Pearson Correlation	.244*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.014	
	N	100	100

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Primary Data

H0: There is no significant relationship between television advertising and the cosmetics acquired by women consumers. The above table shows the relationship between television advertising and the cosmetics acquired by women consumers is persuaded by television advertising and the p-value is 0.014 which is less than 0.05 hence we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. The value of $r = 0.244$ shows that it was positively correlated and there is a significant relationship between television advertising and the cosmetics acquired by women consumers.

Rehman et. al. (2014) found that the results of correlation indicates that advertising is positively correlated with buying behavior and factors of rural areas ($r = .414$, $r = .632$). Further, buying behavior is negatively correlated with the factors rural areas ($r = -.531$). It can be inferred that advertising has positive effect on buying behavior because the consumers may like advertisements or it may provide required information's. Another reason advertisement may be the source of awareness as the consumers may discuss about it with their friends and family members. It also can be inferred that lot of people are living in mountain areas and have limited access to communication sources like TV, Newspaper etc, so getting advertisement through mobile may be interesting to them.

Table 5 shows the significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and socioeconomic variables.

S. No.	Socio-economic variables	Chi square value	Degrees of Freedom	p value	S-Significant/ NS-Not Significant
1	Age	25.470	20	0.184	NS
2	Educational Qualification	10.498	12	0.572	NS
3	Occupation	26.768	16	0.044	S
4	Marital Status	3.843	4	0.428	NS
5	Type of Family	6.114	4	0.191	NS

Source: Primary Data

H0: There is no significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and socioeconomic variables.

The above table 5 shows that one of the socioeconomic variable occupation wise classification of the respondents is significant with the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising. The other socio-economic variable is not significant therefore there is no significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and age, educational qualification, marital status and type of family of the respondents.

The chi-square value for the age wise classification of the respondents and the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising is 25.470 and p-value is 0.184 which is greater than 0.05 hence it is not significant and there is no significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and age wise classification of the respondents. Table 5 shows that chi-square value for the educational qualification of the respondents and the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising is 10.498 and p-value is 0.572 > 0.05 which is not significant and there is no significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and educational qualification of the respondents. The chi-square value for the occupation of the respondents and the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising is 26.768 and p-value is 0.044 which is less than 0.05 hence it is significant and it was observed that there is a significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and occupation of the respondents. From the above table 5, it was found that the chi-square value for the marital status of the respondents and the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising is 3.843 and p-value is 0.428 > 0.05 hence it is not significant and there is no significant association between the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and the marital status of the respondents. The chi-square value for the Type of Family of the respondents and the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising is 6.114 and p-value is 0.191 which is greater than 0.05 hence it is not significant and therefore there is no significant association between the

attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and the type of family of the respondents.

The researcher Rani & Sharma (2016) has observed in their study that on the basis of age of respondents, young people under 20 years (56.33%) believe that advertising plays an important role in selling products. Respondents between 21-50 years (60.91%) also support the same statement about TV advertisements. On the basis of occupation of respondents, those who agree that advertising plays an important role in selling products are employed like intellectual, officials etc. (66.38%), unemployed like household women and students (55.10%). In this study also women consumers strongly agree that television advertising play a vital role in influencing them to purchase the products.

VII. Discussion and Conclusion

The study was concluded that women consumers are influenced by television advertising to acquire cosmetic products. The consumer profile from table 1 discloses that 32% of the respondents are in the age group of less than 25 and 90% of the respondents are graduates. Most of the respondents are working in private concern and their earning is more than 50,000 to 60,000 per month. The 80% of the respondents got married and 69% of the respondents are in the nuclear family and 3 to 4 members are there in the family of 52% of the respondents.

Table 2 shows that among the other variables like family members, friends and workplace television advertising is the variable which influences the purchase decision of women consumers towards cosmetics. Table 3 discloses that music is the attribute that women consumers like very much in cosmetic advertising followed by artist. By using correlation it was found that from table 4 there is a significant relationship between television advertising and the cosmetics acquired by women consumers and the p-value is 0.014. The television advertising convinces women consumers for the money spent on cosmetics and make them

feel charming and to gain more self-belief among others in society.

Table 5 shows the significant association between attributes liked in cosmetic advertising and socioeconomic variables of the women consumers. The socioeconomic variable occupation is significant and $p = 0.044 < 0.05$. The other variables like age, educational qualification marital status and type of family is not significant with the attributes liked in cosmetic advertising. The study was finally concluded that advertising glee and persuade women to buy the cosmetic product.

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